

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 8.1: Waste management in the context of public administration

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from (April 2023) to (March 2024)
Periodic report date and version:	03/04/2024 version 1
Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D8.1	Waste management in the context of public administration	R	PU	12	18/03/2024	Report containing data related waste management creating public value developed in the frame of the project and prepared from emerging public services practices		04/02/2024
D8.2	Defining clear objectives and measuring them by using appropriate indicators	R	PU	18	(Agosto 2024)			
D8.3	Methodology and training contents based on social impact	R	PU	24				
D8.4	Case Study applied to waste management	R	PU	28				
D8.5	Urban waste management	R	PU	30				

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art	Report	10 (Gennaio 2024)	04/02/2024	The investigation of the legal framework.		04/02/2024
M2	Defining the main Stakeholder Mapping		12	18/03/2024	The investigation of the Stakeholder Mapping		04/04/2024
M3	Defining the main social impact and measuring public value creation		18				

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The Deliverable D1 entitled "Waste management in the context of public administration" is started at the beginning of April 2023.

During this period are achieved completely the Milestone M1 titled "Analysis of the state of art" and Milestone M2 named "Defining the main Stakeholder Mapping". The Deliverable has investigated the impact of waste management in public administrations. The different initiatives taken by policy makers will be analysed to identify their economic, environmental and social impact. The goal is to define new perspectives of public value measures on urban waste management on the life of local and global communities.

The research begins by analysing the legal framework and gathering information on the different types of policies already applied. After examine the theoretical framework on public value and social impact, stakeholder mapping was conducted to comprehend which actors play a crucial role in society and value creation.

The Research Team is composed by Professor Paolo Esposito, Arturo Capasso, Maria Moreno, Riccardo Resciniti, Francesco Rota, Matteo Rossi and Nicola Fontana.

The activities implemented are manifold and consist of:

- Literature review on the theoretical framework;
- Literature review on public value creation developed in the frame of the project;
- Bibliographic collection on stakeholder mapping.

Findings of the analysis are part di 2 papers submitted in two International Scientific Conference.

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UNLOCKING ITALY'S POTENTIAL: MEASURING PUBLIC VALUE IN THE NATIONAL RECOVERY PLAN

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to highlight how measure the public value generated by a National Recovery Plan. For this purpose, the research meticulously examines the funding program and evaluates how it will contribute to the creation of new public value. The interpretative model may be particularly suitable for data collection through the review of European Commission reports and associated literature. Data can be collected through online research methods, enabling the analysis and evaluation of European Commission reports to comprehend how the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) will impact Italy and how it will benefit citizens and governments. The review also underscores how Italy will utilize the PNRR to enhance its economic and social conditions, thereby creating public value.

Keywords: *Public value, PNRR, National Recovery Plan, Social impact.*

Track No: 51. General Track.

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Abstract

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Introduction

European Union has adopted a recovery plan, through Next Generation EU which it aims to help the countries to deal with their economic and social damage, which was caused by the pandemic Covid-19. The European Union has estimated the budget of around €750 billion, out of which €390 billion will be granted by the EU, whereas remaining amount will be in the form of loans for the period of 2021 to 2026 (Esposito et al., 2021). With this fund, the EU aims to support the European countries in becoming greener, more resilient, digital, and better. This will also help them to meet the future challenges. Not only this, but also the digital platforms have helped the medical departments to continue their services via tele-health and help the nations to recover as soon as possible. Moreover, it also helped the countries to stabilize their economic condition via digital dealings and prevent market breakdown or shortage of resources for the people. The deliveries were made at home to ensure the availability of everything in the country and to prevent collapse of many businesses (Hirsch-Kreinsen, 2021). Thus, it proved that digital networking proved to be the backbone of the society and thus the European nations understood that they need to invest more in this sector to speed up their developments in high-quality connectivity. It has changed people's perspectives

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and now healthcare services can be provided in any region of the world via tele-health services (Lloyd, 2021). The businesses are offering their products to multiple regions while establishing single headquarter at specific station. This shows that digital connectivity is the best way to expand business, educational, healthcare, social, and awareness associated services throughout the world, and even does not require huge investments such as physical buildings or travel expenditures.

The present document is structured into four distinct sections. The initial section sets the stage by discussing the importance of pioneering research in the realm of public value. Within this section, an overview is provided of the expanding body of literature on public value, focusing specifically on the discourse surrounding frameworks for measuring public value (Papi et al., 2018). After a literature review, we introduce the measuring public value in, generally, an EU Recovery Plan and in, particularly, a National Recovery Plan. The factor at the base on this are the literature gap on the measurement public value and the increasing significance the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) will impact Italy and how it will benefit the public and governments. The methodology and research design, presented in second section, aims to broaden the scope of public value measurement frameworks by describing qualitative approach (Tomaszewski, et al., 2020). Third section discusses results of the research and proposes some recommendations for enhancement in terms of public value. It describes the examinations conducted to assess the stated hypotheses, the results of which progressively contribute to resolving the research inquiry. Furthermore, important insights pertaining to the public value theme are investigated to furnish practitioners with a groundwork. Fourth section discusses certain constraints of the study and suggests how the research framework could be applied for future investigations.

Theoretical Framework: Measuring Public Value

The COVID-19 pandemic on a global scale has prompted various local governments to upgrade their digital interface, providing a wider range of programs and services online and moving towards online platforms for engaging with the public. In order to provide an overall view of a company or entity's ability to create value for citizens and stakeholders, it is becoming common to consider various evaluation measures in addition to purely economic ones (Cohen and Karatzimas, 2015; Fordham et al., 2018). Additionally, to acquire a more profound comprehension of the particular idea of public worth, as estimated by a public value

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scale, and to compare it with other relevant social evaluation frameworks, we included a corporate social responsibility and reputation scale in our survey. Although there is an intersection between these concepts, they also present noteworthy variations (Meynhardt, et al. 2019). While Integrated Popular Reporting is geared toward measuring through the six capitals the consumption of value and the realization of public services, there is a lack of research examining whether the tool has the capacity to measure the generation or depletion of public value. (Cohen and Karatzimas, 2015; Biondi and Bracci, 2018).

Firstly, Moore (2007) identifies three specific rationales for the significance of measuring public value: to adhere with external accountability mandates, to define a distinct and meaningful mission and objective for the organization, and to cultivate a robust “sense of internal accountability” (Moore, 2007). While (2007) Moore emphasizes the importance of accountable public managers for the creation of public value, he does not provide a clear answer to the question “how do you measure public value?” in creating public value. Mendel and Brudney (2014) argue that the concept of public value remains unclear, receiving scant attention and being surrounded by speculation. Furthermore, considerations of efficiency involve evaluating whether the appropriate measures have been adhered to and executed properly (Kelly et al., 2002). The assertion made by Donahue and Miller (2006) underscores the fiscal stress experienced by local governments due to limited public funds and increasing need for public services, compelling them to strive for greater efficiency.

Meanwhile, Epstein (2003) suggests correlation between high public value scores and the fulfillment of basic needs should potentially lead to favorable attitudes and behavior. Faulkner and Kaufman (2018) present a framework with four key themes for evaluating public value, covering aspects such as public satisfaction, economic value, political value, financial performance, non-financial performance, trust, and legitimacy. Cwiklicki (2016) observed a rise in the number of recommended “public value measurement frameworks” in his literature review over the last decade. For instance, social entrepreneurship offers a valuable resource for creating public value (Chandra and Paras, 2021). Additionally, Meynhardt and Jasinenko (2021) view value “as multi-faceted, encompassing hedonistic-aesthetical, utilitarian-instrumental, political-social, and moral-ethical dimensions”. The gluttonous stylish aspect includes an emphasis on expanding delight, bliss, and unwinding, while the utilitarian-instrumental aspect envelops the interests in understanding, foreseeing, and controlling the climate, holding back nothing, monetary or financial worth. The political-social viewpoint connects with worries encompassing social character, feeling of having a place, and gathering

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participation, though the moral aspect depends on the drive for confidence and poise, individual moral and moral standards, uniformity, and reasonableness.

Although there is no universally applicable metric for public value, endeavors have been undertaken to construct methodologies for this objective. Consequently, several frameworks have been devised with the goal of comprehending public value.

Methodology and Research Design

The data analysis was conducted by employing a systematic approach that involved combining the available information through an inductive process (Dubois and Gadde, 2002). This approach was characterized by integrating the existing literature on the subject and utilizing empirical data. By adopting an analysis of a case study, it becomes feasible to observe the development of trends, changes, and relationships over time. Furthermore, this approach aids in comprehending the underlying motivations behind the evolution of a given situation (Fitzmaurice and Ravichandran, 2008). The case that was selected is the NODES's (Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile - which is the Italian for "Digital and Sustainable North-Western Italy") funded by National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), Mission 4 "Istruzione e ricerca", Component 2 "From research to enterprise" – Investment 1.5, which is in turn financed by the Next Generation EU of European Union (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036). This serves the purpose of bridging the gaps that may arise from relying solely on a single approach.

The interpretative model may be particularly suitable for data collection through the review of European Commission and Italian reports and associated literature. Data can be collected through online research methods, enabling the analysis and evaluation of European Commission reports to comprehend how the PNRR will impact Italy and how it will benefit the public and governments. When digging deep into the European recovery plan, it consists of multiple components, where each component aims to bring social and economic benefits to the European countries. It identified several important risks to the success of the recovery plans, such as lack of focus and bias, illegal project management, slow work and lack of European dimension and capacity to implement such complex services. in addition to the regular EU budget (Núñez Ferrer, Jorge, 2021).

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The authors investigated at both a qualitative approach and an evidence-based exploratory strategy, which is especially advised for researching phenomena that have not been well studied yet (Eisenhardt, 1989) or when it is difficult to distinguish between a phenomenon and its surroundings. This methodology has, then, the merit of ensuring a high degree of insight into the complex reality examined (Berg, 2004) through the use of multiple sources such as evidence analysis, internal company documents, interviews and direct observations. In this regard, it is useful to point out that the implementation of a health expenditure monitoring information system within a regional health context involves the involvement of all public health companies in the system and, therefore, represents a complex process closely linked to the specific organizational context in which it is generated and is influenced by internal and external variables that are difficult to isolate. Multiple research paths can be acquired more easily when an approach influenced by the selection and review of prior research is employed (Khan et al., 2003). For this reason, to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the phenomenon and address the research inquiries presented, it is imperative to thoroughly investigate the subject matter. It was deemed appropriate to use a method capable of capturing both the technical and behavioral aspects that characterize the dynamics of the corporate organizational system under investigation.

Discussion and Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic has provided an opportunity to introduce digital advancement especially in education, industries to cover all financial and social challenges (Amankwah-Amoah, et al., 2021.). The developed countries will be able to facilitate the people with better services and opportunities to live a better life (Baldwin, 2020). Also, it will enable the people of that region to invest in different sectors and improve their contribution towards society (Bailey, et al., 2021). For this purpose, the EU introduced the European Union Recovery Plan, which works on central managed EU funds and thus every member state needs to share funds to help other states. The proposal aimed to highlight how measure the public value generated by a National Recovery Plan. To attain the objective, review of already published reports and literature was done and collected data was analyzed. Firstly, a way to measure public value is through Key Performance Indicators: NODES' Research and Innovation program adopts several KPIs because public value creation effects on citizens, companies and municipalities (Esposito and Tufo, 2023c). The effectiveness and explanatory power of public value were

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evaluated through the inclusion of measures that account for the fundamental variances between public and private sector establishments (Esposito and Tufo, 2023b). Our selection of KPIs was limited to those that could be feasibly applied across all types of organizations. Although willingness to pay more (Donahue et al., 2006) and consumption frequency are commonly employed as performance indicators in the private sector (Bracci et al., 2023), these metrics are also gaining prominence in the evaluation of public sector organizations.

The monitoring and the results evaluation of National Recovery Plan of Italy be run long the three-year period of the research and innovation program and articulated through three dimension of KPI:

- Output KPIs, linked to the activities envisaged in the ecosystem in relation to the WPs implementation.
- Outcome KPIs, linked to what is intended to be generated through the activities of the Ecosystem's Booster.
- Impact KPIs, representative of the impacts that NODOS's intends to generate on the territory in the medium-long term and beyond the period of operation of the project.

In a specific case study analyzed, NODES's partners define specific verification sources in terms of reports, document, and information sources useful for measuring the indicator value. In particular, it is defined methods, tools and frequency used for data collection from NODES partner as well as for information processing from institutional and private actors involved in the local ecosystem (e.g. surveys, interviews, focus group workshops).

The Table 1 summarizes the identification and description KPIs (metrics) through which the monitoring of NODE'S implementation (output and outcomes) and the evaluation of impacts generated on the territory will be measured, as well as relative quantification of the expected targets.

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Actions		Key Indicator (Impact Indicator, Outcome Indicator, Output Indicator)	NODES' overall target
ECOSYSTEM'S ENGAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT BOOSTER	Impact	(Increase of) engagement of the different actors in research and innovation actions within the ecosystem's territories	
		(boosting) innovation demand from industries and civil societies	
		(fostering) internationalization	
Research and Innovation Roadmap development	Outcome	Number of updated NODE's Research and Innovation Roadmaps	14
		Level of participation at Research and Innovation Roadmap's development, according to the principles of representativeness based on different parameters (eg type, size, maturity and geographical location)	At least 7 out of 10 in level of representativeness
	Output	Number of interdisciplinary working groups	14
		Number of collected industrial interest through NODES' entrepreneurial discovery processes	373
Engagement of actors, especially companies and civil society	Outcome	Number of stakeholders (including professionals, entrepreneurs, researchers, administrators, citizens, students) reached through engagement actions	17.500
		Number of member of Spokes' Stakeholder Committees in accordance representativeness based on categories	140
		Level of stakeholder's (firms and civic society) awareness on NODES's activities	At least 7 out of 10 in level of awareness
	Output	Number of organized events/seminars/workshops/infodays/webinar/etc.	50
		Number of B2B and B2R (Meetings businesses to business, businesses and research actors)	630
Mapping of competences and needs and Development of technology-driven value chains	Outcome	NODES' Analysis on research and innovation specialization, competence and needs, opportunities and challenge, according to each Spoke's thematic	21
		Number of established/boosted Spokes' value chains	14
	Output	Number of Ecosystem actors (in particular SMEs), mapped on competence and solutions, research and innovation interest, training and internationalization needs	420
Internationalization	Outcome	Number of established and strengthened collaborations and partnerships with EU and International entities (international research center, clusters, EDIH, associations and initiatives) to enhance NODES' actions, behind the period of the project	28
	Output	Number of mapped EU initiatives	84
Number of international events organized or participated		42	

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		Number of companies/civic societies that participate in international initiatives organized at the local level	210
RESEARCH BOOSTER	Impact	(Increase of) private and public investment in R&D, through research and innovative activities carried out jointly by universities and companies, in particular SMEs, operating in the area (Increase of) business potential in terms of creation and acceleration of high-tech start-ups, development of new/enhanced product/services and/or improved industrial process	
Research activities and Flagship Project	Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	14
		Number of publications	500
		Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	25
	Output	Number of flagship project	14
		Number of professor and researcher involved	368
		Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project	480
Recruitment of new talent	Outcome	Number of researcher and technicians (research and innovation manager)	91
		Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	182
	Output	Number of open positions	91
		Number of applicants	273
COMPETENCE BOOSTER	Impact	(Increase of) Level of soft skill and technological competences gain (Reduction of) the skills mismatch between education and job application (Increase of) demand of highly qualified human capital in terms of number researchers and (young) talents hired by firms	
Lifelong Learning initiatives	Outcome	Number of professionals and managers involved in lifelong learning initiatives, and certified on the knowledge and skills acquired	1,400
		Number of firms involved in LLL initiatives.	160
	Output	Number of LLL initiatives in place	56
		Number of participants (managers involved in executive education programs and specialists involved in innovation initiatives)	1,400
		Number of training hours delivered	4,000
Industrial PhD	Outcome	Number of PhD students specialists certified on the knowledge and skills acquired	25
		Number of tutors specialists involved in innovation initiatives	25
		Number of young and newly graduate specialists hired in companies and involved in R&D&I activities	14
	Output 3	Number of industrial tutors involved in the PhD programs	25
		Number of firms participating at PhD programs	20
		Number of open PhD positions	28
Entrepreneurship training for students and early career researchers	Outcome B	Number of student team willing to develop their own business on the challenge	17
		Number of students and researched that gain a certification on Innovation management and entrepreneurship course	441
	Output 1	Number of training hours	7,000

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		Number of student applicants participating at training course (step2start and Innovation management and entrepreneurship course)	735
		Number of challenges	35
		Number of student applicants to challenge initiatives	700
INNOVATION BOOSTER	Impact	(Increase of) Amount of EU funding raised by SMEs, start-ups and spin-offs	
		(Increase of) Amount of equity fund raising of supported start ups	
		(Increase of) Growth in companies' turnover (SMEs)	
Matchmaking actions	Outcome	Number of technologies that are exploited in entrepreneurial initiatives via PoC, acceleration support services, etc.	30
	Output	Number of technologies (patents, software) shared on KS platforms	200 technologies
		Number of events during which technologies are presented to firms and investors	50
		Number of events organized for the promotion and dissemination of technologies and research results (TechShareDay)	14
Academic PoCs	Outcome	Number of finished POC	22
		Amount of grants	5.6 mln
		Number of established spinoffs	15
		Number of transferred technologies (licensing, assignment, etc.)	20
		Number of granted projects	25
	Output	Number of cut-off dates for Academic PoCs	14
		Number of collected and evaluated PoC proposals	40
Industrial PoCs	Outcome	Number of POC granted projects	90
		Amount of Grants	18.8 Mln
		Amount of industrial investments in PoC Initiatives	37.5 Mln
		Number of funded firms (start-ups, SMEs)	180
		Total amount of research contracts generated within the PoC	3 Mln
	Output	Number of cut-off dates for Industrial PoCs	14
		Number of collected and evaluated PoC proposals	120
ACCELERATION BOOSTER	Impact	(Increase of) Amount of EU funding raised by SMEs, start-ups and spin-offs	
		(Increase of) Amount of equity fund raising of supported start ups	
		(Increase of) Growth in companies' turnover (SMEs)	
Access to finance	Outcome	Number of matchmaking between companies and potential investors/large companies	75
		Number of entrepreneurial projects for feasibility developed, presented by spin-off and SMEs	30
		Number of new start-ups incorporated, focus on NODES' thematic	10
		Number of strategic partnerships between NODES and innovation actors (Acceleration, Bank Foundations, Venture Capitalist) signed to support acceleration, scaling-up and access to finance	21
	Output	Number of involved SMEs and starts-up in the acceleration activities	200

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		Number of start-ups and project supported in national and international funding calls	15
		Number of organized events to foster the dialogue between firms and large companies/venture capitalists	21
Market development	Outcome	Number of generated matchmakings with technological and business partners, as well as investors	300
		Number of Acceleration vouchers granted	280
		Number of funded SMEs and start-ups	100
		Amount of grants	11.5Mln
	Output	Number of listed acceleration services	15
		Number of applicants (SMEs and starts-up)	350

Figure 1. NODES' KPIs

Overall, the collected funds will be given to the desiring member states as loan, which it can be used for its regional and digital development and can pay back as per the EU recovery plan policies. Especially, when concerned about the new public value (Esposito and Ricci, 2015), people want development in the sector which may increase chances of employment, better healthcare opportunities, and more business investments in the region. Thus, with the advancement in network connectivity, the country will bring more outsourcing opportunities for the people. Especially, it will help people of remote areas to work from home, get better education, and get better employments without even leaving their home. Not only this, but also advanced digital technology will improve healthcare facilities for all, where the people in remote areas will also get access to tele-health on time.

Limitations and further research

A possible disadvantage is the use of a dataset, which could be overcome in the future because of the advent of AI (Artificial Intelligence) may undergo modifications several fields: economics, finance, education system, security and automotive (Esposito and Tufo, 2023a).

In the debate about public value measurement, according to Esposito et al. (2024), further research will investigate on renewable energy communities. Furthermore, all States must establish a proper report regarding how they consumed EU Recovery Plan and what outcomes were achieved through its associated funds. This will also be helpful for the EU and other organizations to propose other recovery plans and financial aids to the States in future. In particular, the reports must include the suggestions regarding how coming plans can be improved with respect to loan return policy or other financial and social measures. In this way better recovery plans will be introduced in future, which will bring more opportunities for the States to strengthen their GDP and gain more financial and social outcomes.

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Retracing public value creation through digital and sustainable transformation. A Recovery Plan case study

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Abstract

The focal pillars of digital transformation and sustainability have spurred the implementation of various strategies through policy interventions in production, distribution, and consumption processes. As societies grapple with the intricacies of this paradigm shift, comprehension of how public administration shapes the delivery of public services to meet sustainability imperatives assumes paramount importance, yielding public value in the process. In the current era, the delineation of public value arises from the nuanced interplay of socio-political dynamics, advancements in information and communication technology (ICT), and an unwavering commitment to the pillars of sustainable development within the public sector. Scholarly discourse accentuates the imperative for a multidisciplinary approach to effectively address these multifaceted challenges. The analysis was conducted using the case study method to trace public value creation through digital and sustainable transformation in NODES' Research and Innovation program financed by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP or PNRR) that is part of the Next Generation EU (NGEU). NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, the article examines all the 7 Spokes. In particular, Spoke 2 entitled “Green Technologies and Sustainable Industry” carries out systemic solutions at local scale with a strong emphasis on the key elements of sustainable development: economic prosperity, environmental protection and social equity, balancing these three dimensions in order to benefit current and future generations. The nexus among sustainability, digital transformation, and the interrelation of social, economic, and environmental values constitutes the crux of this endeavor. These factors are the fundament of Spoke 3 titled “Tourism and Culture Industry” that aims at developing an open infrastructure for immersive virtual reality systems for research and

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educational purposes. The project is based on the architecture of a collaboration platform able to integrate advanced technologies and human expertise. By illuminating the interconnectedness between financial management, imperatives of sustainability, and societal well-being, the findings will be developed to obtain new jobs in the short/medium term, thanks to improved policy support from governing bodies and creating new business solutions. In doing so, they not only foster enduring public value but also fortify societal resilience in the face of evolving challenges.

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Keywords: public value creation, digital transformation, sustainable transformation, Recovery Plan

Subject classification codes: include these here if the journal requires them

Introduction

The Covid-19 Pandemic has hit the entire world so hard, due to which the countries and states have been facing several financial and trading issues. Several governments also made new plans to deal with such financial crises and to recover their loss with effective strategies. Thus, the European Union has also adopted a recovery plan, through which it aims to help the countries to deal with their economic and social damage, which was caused by the pandemic Covid-19. The European Union has estimated the budget of around €750 billion, out of which €390 billion will be granted by the EU, whereas remaining amount will be in the form of loans for the period of 2021 to 2026 (Esposito et al., 2021). With this fund, the EU aims to support the European countries in becoming greener, more resilient, digital, and better. This will also help them to meet the future challenges. In the current era, the delineation of public value arises from the nuanced interplay of socio-political dynamics, advancements in information and communication

technology (ICT), and an unwavering commitment to the pillars of sustainable development within the public sector. There is also a strong convergence on thinking that the sources of competitiveness and value creation (Cui, T., & Osborne 2022), both for public and private collaboration (Esposito & Tufo, 2023b), are progressively and irreversibly shifted from tangible to intangible factors. Therefore, with reference to the research purpose and bearing in mind the specific analysis targets the paper is structured as follows. In paragraph 2, attention is paid to the literature review on public value. While in paragraph 3 the methodological approach and Research Questions are defined, section 4 presents the principal findings of the case study are expounded upon. Ultimately, paragraph 5 encompasses concluding considerations, addresses limitations, and outlines potential avenues for future research.

Theoretical framework: literature review

In academic literature, public value was identified by several scholars (Moore, 1994; Puron-Cid et al., 2008; Hartley et al., 2017; Hay & Cordery, 2018; Bracci et al., 2021; Hartley et al., 2024). Public value refers to the efficient, impartial, and transparent delivery of public services, organizations, and policies for the betterment of society and the satisfaction of stakeholders (Cluley et al., 2020; Osborne et al., 2021; Osborne et al., 2022). This concept encompasses the optimal utilization of resources, fostering engagement, establishing a reciprocal relationship, and upholding democratic principles and overall welfare (O'Flynn, 2021; Nicolò et al., 2023). Public value pragmatism at three distinct levels pertaining to programmes, institutions, and entire public sectors can be a way forward that demand collaboration at multiple stages (Alford & Hughes, 2008). Research in the areas of governance is necessary because they play a crucial role in

enabling the creation of public value (Esposito et al., 2020). In the current era, the delineation of public value arises from the nuanced interplay of socio-political dynamics, advancements in information and communication technology (ICT), and an unwavering commitment to the pillars of sustainable development within the public sector. The creation of value demands the capability to plan, supervise, and govern both tangible and intangible resources, while also orchestrating the actions of the involved parties (Van Gestel et al., 2023). Scholars have been progressively converging on the institutional emphasis of policymakers' endeavors (Jaspers & Steen, 2021). The sustainability of a region's competitive advantage hinges on its ability to fulfill the expectations of various local stakeholders (individuals and/or organizations) who are part of the value creation process, either directly or indirectly (Aversano et al., 2020). It is not a one-way street but a two-way sword so vigilance is advised for collaborative efforts to have public value and not public (dis)value (Esposito & Ricci, 2015). In instance, there are practical limitations to extensive innovation, which goes beyond the current policy frameworks and services to provide public value (van Gestel & Grotenbreg, 2021). The concept of public value involves measuring the effectiveness of government actions in delivering value to its citizens (Jain Gupta & Suri, 2017). Indeed, the literature review highlights gap in measuring public value in EU Recovery Plan. Previously, research was conducted on: Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Nugraha et al., 2023) and PDSE “Post-Disaster Social Entrepreneurship” (Chandra & Paras, 2021). Scholarly disclosure emphasises the imperative of a multidisciplinary approach to effectively address these multifaceted challenges.

Methodology and Research Design

To pursue the research aim, authors adopt a case study method. This approach is suitable when the investigator aims to comprehend an intricate occurrence within a particular setting, with the objective of offering an examination of the setting and procedures that shed light on the theoretical matters being examined (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007; Yin, 2003; Yin, 2017). Consequently, it is especially fitting for the current research as it concentrates on the EU Recovery Plans. Out of all EU member states, Italy was the hardest hit one by COVID-19. However, the lockdown affected the economy of the country in worst way and resulted as 9% decline of its GDP in 2020. This was approximately loss of €156 billion. The impact of this was not limited to the business sector alone; rather, it extended to various other industries such as food services, hospitality, healthcare, and social services, all of which experienced significant disruptions (Pesole, 2020). For this reason, the analysis was conducted using the case study method to trace public value creation through digital and sustainable transformation in NODES’ Research and Innovation program funded by National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), Mission 4 “Istruzione e ricerca”, Component 2 “From research to enterprise” – Investment 1.5, which is in turn financed by the NextGenerationEU (NGEU) of European Union (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036). NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities.

Based on the literature review, The investigation is focused on resolving the Research Questions:

RQ 1: How does the EU Recovery Plan create public value?

RQ 2: How to measure public value in the EU Recovery Plan?

Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, the article examines all the 7 Spokes. The results and findings will be presented in the next paragraph of the research.

Findings

This research highlighted the significance of measure public value during EU Recovery Plan. NODES (Nord-Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile - which is the Italian for “Digital and Sustainable North-Western Italy”) encompasses regions in Piemonte, Valle D’Aosta, and neighboring provinces of Lombardia (Pavia, Como, and Varese). It is comprised of 24 innovation entities, including universities, innovation clusters, research centers, competence centers, incubators, and accelerators. These entities are closely connected to the productive and research strengths that showcase the excellence of the respective regions. NODES is structured into 7 distinct spokes, each with a unique emphasis falling within the realms of digital and ecological transitions:

- Spoke 1: Industry 4.0 For Sustainable Mobility and Aerospace
- Spoke 2: Green Technologies and Sustainable Industry
- Spoke 3: For Culture and Tourism Industry
- Spoke 4: Digital Innovation Toward Sustainable Mountain
- Spoke 5: Industry for Health and Silver Economy
- Spoke 6: Primary Agroindustry

- Spoke 7: Secondary Agroindustry

NODES' Research and Innovation program is strategically designed to ensure interdisciplinary collaboration across a range of themes and promote the cross-pollination of digital-driven technology and innovation. The overarching goal of NODES is to enhance the competitiveness of industries and research institutions, positioning the region as an attractive "territorial system" for high-skilled talents and private investments at both national and international levels. To achieve this objective, NODES is dedicated to addressing the structural deficiencies highlighted in the PNRR by implementing new collaborative approaches, tools, and activities to tackle strategic innovation challenges and drive positive impacts in the realms of digital and ecological transition. Furthermore, NODES is committed to supporting the specific objectives outlined in the PNRR related to "Digital, Industry, Aerospace". NODES activities respond to the challenges of digital and ecological transition with specific reference to the area of specialization: Digital, Industry, Aerospace. The ambition is to valorize the great industrial potential of the district, in terms of existing competences and skills, and to prepare companies in general and SMEs in particular to the forthcoming digital and ecological revolution.

The objective of Spoke 1 “Industry 4.0 for Sustainable Mobility and Aerospace” is to improve the innovation capabilities and the competitiveness of local firms in the areas of sustainable mobility and aerospace, including the related enabling infrastructures, both physical and digital. The key long-termed technological trajectories that are already disrupting the competence mix of local companies are linked to the transition towards low-carbon mobility systems and the development of new space infrastructures and services. The shift in technological paradigms engendered by electrification, adoption of sustainable propulsion systems and sustainable materials, reduction in the access to space costs, servitization in manufacturing, pervasive use of

advanced digital technologies in design and operations imply an architectural transformation of the mobility and aerospace sectors and a contextual redefinition of the role of SMEs in supply chains. Concerning the area of aerospace, the research and innovation program of Spokes 1 appears to be synergic and complementary also to the activities in the PNRR Partenariato Esteso n. 15 Space Activities.

Spoke 2, titled "Green Technologies and Sustainable Industry," focuses on the adoption and utilization of Circular Economy strategies in both upstream and downstream operations. The primary objective is to establish environmentally friendly industrial processes while simultaneously repurposing and recycling industrial, agricultural, and civil waste materials, as well as mineral byproducts. At a local level, Spoke 2 implements comprehensive solutions that prioritize the fundamental aspects of sustainable development, including economic growth, environmental preservation, and social fairness, balancing these three dimensions in order to benefit current and future generations. As an output, the creation of a portal for the mapping of by-products and (biomass and mineral) waste represents the proof-of-concept for the development of an online platform for the matchmaking between materials and conversion technologies proposed and implemented already. The applied research and the flagship project of the spoke will have synergies with National Innovation Infrastructure for the “Simulation and Monitoring of the Energy System” (PNRR Mission 4).

The research and innovation program of Spoke 3 “Culture and Tourism Industry” is fully aligned with the research area 5.2 of the National Research Program 2021-2027 (PNR) "Humanistic culture, creativity, social transformation, society of inclusion", which identifies investments in heritage, as well as falling within the logic of sustainability, also with reference to the energy transition underway, feed both direct and indirect value production chains and, above all, crossover effects, which respond to the economic

models of creative cultural industries and digital platforms. The intensive and extensive application of digital technologies to cultural heritage (tangible and intangible) and the interoperability of the data produced respond to the dual objective of reducing the time and cost of conservation and making it accessible to a wide audience, while ensuring high standards of protection and quality of interventions. Within the large area "Humanistic culture, creativity, social transformation, society of inclusion" of the NRP, the area of intervention "Creativity, design and Made in Italy", in accordance with the targets of the European Commission chaired by Ursula von der Leyen and with the aims of Pillars II and III of Horizon Europe, collects the challenges of the economic and productive system of Italy, a country system that focuses on Made in Italy and export its real economy, its culture, its design and creative capacity, through the main productive areas of the 4A (furniture-home, food- Eno gastronomy, clothing-fashion, automation-mechanics) and, in general, of the creative industries.

Spoke 4 named “Digital Innovation Toward Sustainable Mountain” aims at developing tools, demonstrators, and best practices to enhance digital contents of firms and sustainability of productions in mountain regions. The digital dimension is analysed in three main directions:

- 1) Innovative smart working, new digital compliance procedures, and new digital organizational models;
- 2) Innovative digital tools for managing energy and water resources and infrastructures;
- 3) New organizational models of society and regeneration of mountain territories.

The Spoke’s activities are fully synergic with others envisaged within the Next Generation Italia plan (PNRR), covering three major assets: Mission 1, Digitalization,

innovation, competitiveness; Mission 2, Green Revolution and Ecological Transition; Mission 5, Social inclusion and cohesion.

Spoke5 titled “Industry for Health and Silver Economy” promotes the interaction between Public Research and health care system, SMEs and global/large companies, aiming to develop digital, innovative and sustainable technologies for the management of frail subjects. The challenges are concentrated in the following themes: personalized, precision and predicted medicine; biomaterials, biotechnologies and technologies for the earlier diagnostic; nutraceuticals, nutrigenomics and functional foods; technologies for mountain medicine (telemedicine, home care and assistance for the chronically ill). The research and innovation program of this spoke is aligned with the research area 5.1 of the National Research Program 2021-2027 "Health", with a specific focus on Silver Economy.

The object of Spoke 6 “Primary Agroindustry” is to develop key enabling digital technologies to evaluate and improve the sustainability of agricultural productions for industrial transformation. The project is strictly focused on the main agricultural productions for food industries in the north-western part of Italy. The thematic research area of Spoke 6 revolves around the sustainable advancement of heavily agricultural areas, utilizing an interdisciplinary and specialized strategy. This strategy amalgamates competencies and expertise from a variety of disciplines, including biosensing, data collection and management, AI, ICT, and exposomics. The primary expected outcome of the project is the development of novel services and business models for the agricultural industry, and it will entail the optimization of business operations, maximization of return and minimization of production costs, but, at the same time the reduction of the environmental impact.

The general aim of the Spoke 7 entitled “Secondary Agroindustry” is to strongly contribute to the innovation and increase of the competitiveness of the agri-food processing system in North-Western Italy framed by the Po River and the Alps-Appennine Mountain range, where the food sector has an elevated level of specialization, specifically in the management and enhancement of agricultural and livestock resources. However, the strengthening of the food production system is needed to face the new environmental and societal challenges, to contribute to the reposition of the North-Western economy in a period of accelerated transformation of production structures at every territorial level, and to maximize the positive impact on the society.

Spokes 6 and Spoke7 draws from multiple funding sources: PNRR funds for Research Infrastructure; PNRR funds for National Center on Agricultural Technology and PNRR funds for National Center on Biodiversity and Human Well Being,

The total budget for NODES’ ECOSYSTEM is 125.15 M€: 14.5M€ are dedicated to the HUB for management and administrative expenses (2.5M€) and for the redevelopment of the HUB Center (12M€); and 110.7M € to NODES’ Spokes implementation. NODES’ consortium assumed a funding rate of 100% of the eligible costs for universities for all envisaged type of actions⁶ and 50% for all other partners involved in the Ecosystem, thus the overall requested PNRR contribution is equal to 119M €. As mentioned before, a total amount of 110.7M € is dedicated for the Ecosystem actions and allocated to 7 Spokes as shown in Figure 1: each Spoke’s budget is within a range of 12% - 19% of the total amount.

Figure 1. NODES's budget breakdown for Spokes (M€)

NODES' Research and Innovation program paid extreme attention to the budget construction, privileging the use of human resources and setting on a limited level the expenses for the other direct costs. Nevertheless, some external costs are indispensable for the good implementation of NODES. The 110.7M€ are breakdown in personnel costs for a total value of 30.7€M, direct costs for a value of € 31.7M and cascade fund allocation for € 48.2M (equal to 40% of the overall NODES' Ecosystem). The direct costs are comprehensive of administrative, indirect cost (for 24% of direct costs, around €7.6M), subcontracting cost and other direct cost for equipment/infrastructure, goods, and services (for 76%, around €24.4M). Part of the Direct costs for equipment/infrastructure, goods, and services is aimed to pilot lines, demonstrators, and prototypes development in relation to NODES. In fact, 18% of the total direct costs (€ 5.73M) has been allocated to foster the creation of academic spin-offs (Academic PoCs). The Figure 2 below shows the breakdown of Cascade Funds in NODES' initiatives envisaged within the Boosters.

Figure 2. NODES' Cascade funds allocation (%)

Around €13.75M are allocated for the recruitment of researcher and technician; € 3.72M are allocated for training vouchers and Industrial PhD grants for SMEs and start-ups; € 16.93M are dedicated to Industrial PoCs and € 10.35M for Acceleration voucher.

Implications and Conclusion

The following research trajectories address the previous Research Questions. The answer to *RQ 1: How does the EU Recovery Plan create public value?* reveal that at the macro level the NODES' Research and Innovation program provides the framework conditions and background context for the effective implementation and replication of circular economy practices, including government, rules and enforcement of the social system, coordinating the institution that support the structure and organisation, while in the meso and micro level concrete circular solutions pave the way to concrete application of circular business models. EU Recovery Plan creates public value not only con a process improvement of public investments but also, through NODES, integrates sustainable development components, facilitating the advancement of a region in achieving its particular objectives across the three principal categories of sustainability: societal fairness, financial well-being, environmental excellence. Greater transparency of

information and the creation of virtual connections between the actors will facilitate the transition of the regional economy towards the circularity paradigm. The essence of this project is rooted in the integration of sustainability, digital transformation, and the interplay between social, economic, and environmental values.

To respond *RQ 2: How to measure public value in the EU Recovery Plan?* it is necessary to elucidate that measurement of public value is not tied to the nature of public undertakings, but rather to the proficiency and efficacy in executing these undertakings, regardless of their particular focus. In doing so, they not only foster enduring public value but also fortify societal resilience in the face of evolving challenges. Therefore, public managers have a duty to ensure the protection and preservation of the public interest, always prioritizing the well-being of their citizens or users over their own personal interests. Firstly, a way to measure public value is through Key Performance Indicators: NODES’ Research and Innovation program adopts several KPIs because public value creation affects on citizens, companies and municipalities (Esposito & Tufo, 2023c). Thus, Figure 3 provide the outcomes and impacts of public value creation involving companies and stakeholders of NODES.

Figure 3. NODES' Activities-Outcomes-Impacts

By illuminating the interconnectedness of financial management, sustainability imperatives and societal welfare, the outlook suggests that new jobs can be created in the short to medium term through improved political support from governing bodies and the creation of new business solutions. generates a potential on which Italy's soft power is based, with positive repercussions also on contiguous economic sectors such as tourism and the creative and cultural industry, showing a significant growth potential but not yet fully expressed, to be exploited through integrated logics and strategies and a strong connection between research, territories, administrations, businesses, and human capital.

Future research trajectories and limitations

In the debate about public value creation, according to Esposito et al. (2024), further research will investigate on renewable energy communities. Digital

transformation has led to an unprecedented transition to mass smart working, outsourcing, business, living standards and leisure in life. With the advent of AI (Artificial Intelligence), several fields of application may undergo modifications: economics, finance, education system, security and automotive (Esposito & Tufo, 2023a). Therefore, sudden transformations may hit the public value, which could be destroyed or eroded.

A possible limitation is that the research was predicated on a singular case study and as such, the outcomes, although of a probing nature, are not transferable to analogous settings. It is therefore imperative to advance the research by expanding the investigative scope, either through qualitative means (such as building upon the original case study methodology and including more similar cases) and/or via quantitative avenues (such as delving into descriptive or inferential analyses).

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The author declare that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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